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IMPACT OF THE INITIATIVES FOR THE SOCIAL REINTEGRATION OF FORMERLY INCARCERATED INDIVIDUALS

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IMPACT OF THE INITIATIVES FOR THE SOCIAL REINTEGRATION OF FORMERLY INCARCERATED INDIVIDUALS

Executive Summary

The primary objective of this study is to examine initiatives aimed at the social reintegration of individuals who have exited the prison system in Brazil and around the world, based on evaluations conducted over the past ten years. While the *Guide for the Social Inclusion of Formerly Incarcerated Individuals (2024)*¹ focused on understanding the main models and strategies implemented by these initiatives, this publication seeks to analyze the impacts and outcomes of these initiatives on the lives of former inmates, whether from the perspective of recidivism or the assurance of rights.

We mapped 32 evaluative publications related to 21 initiatives, both national and international. From this dataset, we concentrated our analysis on those addressing the impact of the initiatives and that comply with the methodological robustness criteria established for this study. Consequently, we selected a subsample of 13 evaluations corresponding to nine initiatives. A detailed analysis was conducted on initiatives with highly robust methodological impacts, classifying their effects as positive, moderate, mixed, negative, or inconclusive. For each initiative, we present its **objectives, strategies, assumptions, and evaluated impacts**.

The research identified six initiatives with a positive impact on supporting formerly incarcerated individuals, categorized into four main areas: individual autonomy and social interaction (two), productive inclusion (one), health (one), and housing (two). Only one initiative, focused on housing, was evaluated as having a moderate impact. Another, centered on productive inclusion, showed mixed results. A third initiative, targeting individual autonomy and social interaction, was deemed inconclusive.

Key initiatives include **Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme** (United Kingdom), which promotes autonomy and social interaction by providing personalized support to women leaving the prison system. This program achieved notable outcomes, with 95% of participants living in stable housing and 67% employed. The **Community Mediation Maryland Reentry Mediation** (United States), which strengthens family bonds through pre-release mediation, reduced recidivism by 13% and extended the time to reoffense. The **Reentry Housing Pilot Program** (United States), which provided housing assistance conditional on treatment and job searching, lowered recidivism rates (21.6% compared to 35.6%) before being discontinued due to budget cuts.

Vision Housing (United Kingdom), which offers housing and support through a network of landlords and continuous assistance, demonstrated a positive impact on reducing recidivism, particularly among women and young people, with statistically significant results over time. The **Skill Mill** (United Kingdom and Estonia), employing young individuals in productive activities such as water management and horticulture, reduced recidivism, and the severity of offenses. Finally, the **Transitions Clinic Network** (United States), which serves individuals with chronic health conditions or those over 50 years old, reduced technical violations² and incarceration time, although overall recidivism rates were comparable to the control group.

Conducting evaluations on the performance and outcomes of social reintegration initiatives and policies allows for a better understanding of what works and how it works. These evaluations have a direct impact on the continuity and maintenance of programs targeting formerly incarcerated individuals by validating their foundations, improving initiatives, enhancing outcomes, and increasing the efficiency of resource allocation. Beyond their direct effects, evaluations can indirectly influence public policy planning and judicial reforms.³ They offer a solid foundation for public administrators and civil society members to replicate national and international proposals while acknowledging the need to adapt them to diverse local contexts.

The process of selecting the sample for this research was particularly challenging. Of the 128 publications analyzed, covering 83 initiatives, only 21 included evaluations, and nine were associated with initiatives whose impact was assessed. This finding highlights a significant gap in evaluative production, revealing the neglect of this critical aspect in the field under study. Therefore, it is essential not only to invest in expanding the availability of programs aimed at formerly incarcerated individuals but also to ensure high-quality evaluations that support evidence-based decision-making.

Introduction

The social reintegration⁴ of formerly incarcerated individuals⁵ is a global challenge requiring justice system reforms, the strengthening of the rule of law, and the implementation of initiatives tailored to the specific needs of this population. After leaving prison, individuals face numerous obstacles, including stigmatization, broken familial bonds, lack of employment opportunities, and limited access to essential services and basic living conditions, such as document regularization, food, transportation, housing, education, and physical and mental healthcare. These challenges are often exacerbated by preexisting vulnerabilities, such as low educational attainment, insufficient financial resources, and substance abuse, which frequently persist or worsen during and after incarceration.⁶

Brazil has one of the largest prison populations globally, with 663,906 individuals confined in physical cells despite having a capacity for 489,991, resulting in 135.49% overcrowding in penitentiary units.⁷ Access to rights such as education and work is inadequate within prisons and largely neglected after release. In this context, investing in social reintegration interventions is critical to ensuring the effective return of formerly incarcerated individuals to society, helping to break cycles of criminal recidivism and marginalization.⁸

Upon leaving prison, formerly incarcerated individuals face an adverse environment with few or insufficient support options, as evidenced by the significantly lower allocation of public resources compared to other areas of Brazilian public security. In 2022, across the budgets of twelve Brazilian states, funding for police patrols amounted to R\$53.3 billion, prisons received R\$12.7 billion, while post-release reintegration programs were allocated only R\$12 million.⁹ This indicates that other areas are funded at levels 4,000 times higher than initiatives aimed at individuals exiting the prison system, reflecting the low priority given to this issue by the Brazilian state.

This low level of investment results in a significant shortage of initiatives targeting formerly incarcerated individuals. Among the few existing initiatives, only a portion undergoes any form of evaluation, and an even smaller fraction is subjected to systematic and rigorous evaluations capable of generating solid evidence about their impacts. This limitation hinders the identification of successful interventions, compromising not only their implementation but also the continuity, improvement, and expansion of essential initiatives for social reintegration and the transformation of policies aimed at formerly incarcerated individuals.

Expanding investments in policies for formerly incarcerated individuals is crucial to increasing the availability of initiatives, with a need to ensure resources are allocated for evaluating these actions. Evaluations help identify what works, for whom, and under what circumstances, providing critical evidence to effectively address the multiple needs of this population and to allocate public resources more efficiently.

In this research, we mapped and described the set of evaluations found, presenting a detailed analysis of the impact of initiatives with robust evaluations targeting formerly incarcerated individuals. The goal is to provide input for building more effective policies and contribute to strengthening this agenda. We advocate for both the expansion of existing initiatives that have demonstrated positive or moderate impacts and the improvement of evaluation standards to maximize results in a frequently neglected field.

Initiatives and Evaluations

Description of Evaluated Initiatives

We begin the presentation of results with an analysis of the full set of 21 initiatives described in the 32 evaluation documents.¹⁰ To characterize these 21 initiatives, the following criteria were used: target audience (whom they are directed at), location (where they were implemented), purpose (their main objectives), and responsible parties (who implements and funds them).

In terms of **target audience**, the evaluated initiatives are directed at formerly incarcerated individuals¹¹ and their family.¹² Additionally, 13 of the 21 initiatives focus on specific groups within the primary audience of formerly incarcerated individuals. The main groups identified are women,¹³ Black and Indigenous people,¹⁴ young adults aged 18 to 24,¹⁵ individuals with mental disorders, those with substance dependence, individuals with complex health needs¹⁶ and those classified as high-risk and high need.¹⁷

This differentiation is particularly significant, as while the general audience consists of vulnerable formerly incarcerated individuals, certain social markers and specific characteristics can heighten that vulnerability and complicate the social reintegration process. Therefore, it is essential for initiatives to acknowledge this diversity and disaggregate information about the individuals served, considering their sociodemographic characteristics.

Regarding location, the social reintegration initiatives have been implemented in various parts of the world. Of the 21 identified initiatives, nine are in Brazil, seven in the United States, five in the United Kingdom (including one also present in the United Kingdom and Estonia), and one in New Zealand.¹⁸

Regarding the purpose of initiatives targeting formerly incarcerated individuals, we considered the stated objective of each initiative – what it seeks to achieve to support the reintegration of individuals into society after incarceration,¹⁹ answering the question: What are the main objectives? The classification used follows the framework proposed in the *Guide for the Social Inclusion of Formerly Incarcerated Individuals* and includes the following categories:

Table 1. Identified Purposes in the Analyzed Initiatives

Source: Guide for the Social Inclusion of Formerly Incarcerated Individuals, Igarapé Institute, 2024.

Of the 21 analyzed initiatives, nine were classified as targeting **individual autonomy** and **social interaction**, six focusing on **productive inclusion**, three on **housing**, and three on **health**.

Regarding those **responsible for implementation**, the majority of the 21 evaluated initiatives (11, slightly more than half) are implemented by the public sector. These are followed by initiatives carried out by civil society organizations, totaling seven, which corresponds to one-third of the total. Additionally, two initiatives (9%) are executed through collaborations between the public sector, private sector, and civil society organizations, while only one initiative (5%) results from a partnership between the public and private sectors.

The analysis of **initiative funding** shows that most are financed by the public sector, accounting for 71.4% (15 initiatives). Other sources include civil society organizations, responsible for 9.5% (two initiatives). Furthermore, 19% (four initiatives) receive co-financing through partnerships between the public sector, private sector, and civil society organizations. It is worth noting that the source of initiatives funding does not necessarily align with those responsible for their implementation.

Description of the evaluations

The same information used to describe the initiatives was applied to characterize the evaluations, with the addition of evaluation type (process or impact), focus (recidivism and/or assurance of rights), and methodologies employed.

In terms of **location**, among the 32 evaluative publications, Brazil and the United States stand out with twelve evaluations each, accounting for more than two-thirds of the total. Other countries, such as the United Kingdom (seven) and New Zealand (one), report lower numbers.

Regarding those **responsible for conducting** the 32 evaluations, the data indicate that most were carried out by academic actors (20), followed by civil society organizations (nine), business consultancies (two), and partnerships between the public sector and an international organization (one). These figures reveal that, although the public sector is the main implementer of the evaluated initiatives (12 initiatives), it does not necessarily take a significant role in evaluating their outcomes and impacts.

Most evaluations (23) do not explicitly identify the **source of their funding**. Among these, it was found that evaluations not declaring their funding source are predominantly conducted by external actors (17), while a smaller proportion (six) are conducted by internal actors, meaning the same entity responsible for implementing the initiative. Of the nine evaluations that specify their funding source, **seven** are external and **two** internal.

When examining the methodologies adopted by the 32 evaluative publications, three methodological approaches were identified: **qualitative** (10), **quantitative** (11), and **mixed** (11). Each of these approaches utilized a variety of analytical tools according to the focus of the evaluation, whether on analyzing the impact²⁰ or processes²¹ of the initiatives under investigation. Below, the main instruments employed by each research approach are presented.

Table 2. Methodological Designs of the Evaluations

Methodological approach	Number of publications	Instruments commonly used in methodology
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Semi-structured interviews ● Focus Groups ● Non-probabilistic combined sampling (snow ball) ● Participant observation ● Document and literature review ● Field diaries ● Inductive thematic analysis ● Content analysis and thematic categorization 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Questionnaires and surveys ● Control group ● Probabilistic sampling (random and stratified) and non-probabilistic (intentional and convenience) ● Survival analysis: Cox Regression and Kaplan-Meier method ● Difference-in-Differences (DID) analysis ● Hypothesis testing: t-tests, chi-square tests, Variance analysis (Anova) ● Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) ● Linear regression ● Multivariate statistical analyses: multiple regression, factor analysis, cluster analysis 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Semi-structured interviews ● Questionnaires and surveys ● Control group ● Non-probabilistic sampling (intentional and convenience) ● Document and literature review ● Linear regression ● Multivariate statistical analyses: multiple regression, factor analysis, cluster analysis ● Bivariate and multivariate reliability tests: Hausman test and Krippendorff's Alpha ● Content analysis and thematic categorization ● Quantitative processing of qualitative data 	

Source: Prepared by the Igarapé Institute based on proprietary data.

A total of 16 **impact** evaluations, 15 **process** evaluations, and only one evaluation that analyzed both dimensions – **process and impact** – were identified. Among the impact evaluations, 10 were quantitative, three mixed, and three qualitative. For process evaluations, eight were mixed, six qualitative, and only one quantitative. The single evaluation that combined **process and impact** used a qualitative method.²²

Regarding the focus of the evaluations, the analysis revealed a division between those centered on recidivism (7), assurance of rights (18), and both dimensions (7). Evaluations that adopted **recidivism** as the explanatory variable investigated the relationship between the initiative (independent variable) and the likelihood of beneficiaries reoffending in criminal activities (dependent variable), analyzing whether the intervention produced positive or negative effects.

For this analysis, techniques such as logistic regression and Cox survival analysis were employed, enabling researchers to test probabilistic models for the recidivism variable based on determinants such as criminal history, age, and gender. The measurement of the initiatives' impact on recidivism was conducted using administrative data from various government agencies, as well as interviews with formerly incarcerated individuals.²³

On the other hand, the rights-based approach evaluates the impact of an initiative (independent variable) on the social reintegration process (dependent variable). This impact is measured through inclusion and access to essential resources such as healthcare, housing, re-establishment of social and family bonds, and employability, in line with the initiatives' objectives. Unlike recidivism-focused evaluations, those centered on the assurance of rights often employed qualitative or mixed methodologies.

It is worth noting that, in 9 of the 32 evaluations, audience segmentation was applied based on criteria such as gender, race, age, educational level, criminal history, and legal status. These segmentations were incorporated into both the evaluation methodologies and the presentation of results, highlighting specific groups within the priority audience of formerly incarcerated individuals. The diversity of audiences served influences the evaluation of impact, which may vary – being more or less positive – depending on the group or subgroup analyzed in the evaluative publication.

Impact of the Initiatives

This chapter will discuss the impact of initiatives targeting formerly incarcerated individuals, based on robust evaluations that measured their outcomes. It will present which initiatives work, for whom they work, and in what contexts.

Of the 32 publications analyzed, covering 21 initiatives, this chapter focuses on those that include impact evaluations (17 in total), including one that addresses both impact and process. Among these 17 evaluations, 13 were selected for meeting methodological robustness criteria, considering metrics, techniques, sample selection, and intervention periods, corresponding to nine initiatives.

Focusing on impact evaluations enables an assessment of the effectiveness and concrete outcomes of the initiatives, highlighting whether they generate changes aligned with their proposed objectives and revealing their effects on the target audience and the social context in which they are implemented. In contrast, while process evaluations are valuable for making operational adjustments, they do not provide sufficient elements to reflect on the direction of implemented policies or to compare the results with the stated objectives of the intervention.

The criteria applied to the analysis consider **four key questions** to assess the strength of the methodology employed:

- Does the evaluation present measurable metrics used to assess impact?
- Does the evaluation include an objective description of the techniques used for data collection, processing, and analysis?
- Does the evaluation provide a description of the sample size and selection process?
- Does the evaluation describe an intervention period exceeding one year?

Based on these four criteria, a filter was applied, considering the use of metrics, techniques, sample, and intervention period. The use of measurable metrics enables precise assessment of impacts, while the objective description of methodological techniques ensures transparency and reliability in the evaluation process. Defining the sample size and selection process ensures data representativeness, and an intervention period exceeding one year allows the capture of long-term effects. These criteria ensure that evaluations can be interpreted with a higher degree of confidence, contributing to a more robust analysis of the initiatives. Consequently, only evaluations meeting all these criteria were analyzed, ensuring the selected evaluations are replicable and methodologically sound.

The following diagram represents the effort made to determine whether the evaluated initiative achieved the expected outcomes, based on the findings presented in the publication and following the applied methodology.

Initiatives with Robust Impact Evaluations

This chapter provides a detailed description of the subsample comprising nine initiatives analyzed through 13 robust impact evaluation documents. This analysis is a focused subset of the broader description presented in the previous chapter, within the total universe of identified initiatives. As previously noted, the categories of location (where they were implemented), purpose (main objective), and responsible entities (who implements and funds them) were used to characterize the initiatives that passed the methodological robustness criteria.

Of the nine analyzed initiatives, one is in Brazil, five in the United States, and three in the United Kingdom (including one implemented simultaneously in the United Kingdom and Estonia).

Regarding the purpose of the initiatives targeting formerly incarcerated individuals, three were classified as oriented toward **individual autonomy** and **social interaction**, three were focused on **housing**, two addressed **productive inclusion**, and one was centered on **health**.

As for those responsible for implementation, of the nine analyzed initiatives, five were executed by civil society organizations and four were carried out by public sector entities.

The analysis of initiative funding shows that most are financed by the public sector, covering four initiatives. Additionally, two initiatives benefit from co-financing through partnerships involving the public sector, private sector, and civil society organizations. Only three initiatives are exclusively funded by civil society organizations.

Tabela 3. Initiatives with robust impact evaluations

Country	Initiative	Purpose	Responsible for implementation	Responsible for funding
Brazil	Programa de Inclusão Social de Egressos do Sistema Prisional (PrEsp)²⁴	Individual autonomy and social interaction	Public sector	Public sector
United States	Community Mediation Maryland (CMM) Reentry Mediation	Individual autonomy and social interaction	Civil society organization	Civil society organization
United Kingdom	Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme	Individual autonomy and social interaction	Civil society organization	Public and private sectors, and Civil society organization
United Kingdom	Vision Housing	Housing	Civil society organization	Civil society organization
United States	Reentry Housing Pilot Program (RHPP)	Housing	Public sector	Public sector
United States	Returning Home – Ohio	Housing	Civil society organization	Civil society organization
United Kingdom and Estonia	Skill Mill	Productive inclusion	Civil society organization	Public and private sectors, and Civil society organization
United States	Ban the Box	Productive inclusion	Public sector	Public sector
United States	Transitions Clinic Network (TCN)	Health	Public sector	Public sector

Source: Prepared by the Igarapé Institute based on proprietary data.

Assessment of Impacts

Of the nine initiatives evaluated through the 13 publications that met the prioritized focus and the established robustness criteria, impacts were assessed based on five categories: positive impact, moderate impact, mixed impact, negative impact, and inconclusive.

- **Positive Impact:** Attributed to initiatives whose evaluations demonstrated beneficial and effective results, such as reducing recidivism or increasing access to rights, aimed at social reintegration.
- **Moderate Impact:** Attributed to initiatives whose evaluations showed positive results, but in a partial or limited manner, indicating that the effects were not as significant as expected, such as failures to address specific groups adequately.
- **Mixed Impact:** Attributed to initiatives whose evaluations indicated both positive and negative results, including negative externalities, suggesting the need for adjustments to maximize benefits and minimize harm.
- **Negative Impact:** Attributed to initiatives whose evaluations revealed adverse or unintended effects.
- **Inconclusive:** Attributed to initiatives whose evaluations did not allow for determining the impact relative to the stated objectives.

The following assessments were identified for the nine initiatives evaluated:

Table 4. Impact Assessment of Initiatives Based on the Analyzed Evaluations

Initiative	Purpose	Number of Evaluations Analyzed for the Initiative	Evaluation Focus	Initiative Impact Assessment
• Transitions Clinic Network (TCN)	Health	1	Recidivism	Positive impact
• Reentry Housing Pilot Program (RHPP)	Housing	1	Recidivism	Positive impact
• Skill Mill	Productive inclusion	1	Recidivism and rights assurance	Positive impact
• Community Mediation Maryland (CMM) Reentry Mediation	Individual autonomy and social interaction	2	Recidivism	Positive impact
• Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme	Individual autonomy and social interaction	1	Rights assurance	Positive impact
• Vision Housing	Housing	1	Recidivism	Positive impact
• Returning Home - Ohio	Housing	1	Recidivism	Moderate impact
• Ban the Box	Productive inclusion	4	Rights assurance	Mixed impact
• Programa de Inclusão Social de Egressos do Sistema Prisional (PrEsp)	Individual autonomy and social interaction	1	Recidivism and rights assurance	Inconclusive

Source: Prepared by the Igarapé Institute based on proprietary data.

The impact assessment of the evaluated initiatives revealed that, among the nine initiatives analyzed, the majority demonstrated positive impacts. Specifically, six of them received a positive impact evaluation, indicating that these initiatives achieved favorable results aligned with their objectives.

Only one initiative, focused on housing, was rated as having a moderate impact, suggesting that the results were mixed, with positive aspects but also challenges and/or less significant impact. Additionally, one initiative, focused on productive inclusion, was rated as having a mixed impact, indicating that its results were heterogeneous, presenting both positive and negative or limited aspects concerning certain groups. Finally, an initiative aimed at individual autonomy and social interaction was considered inconclusive, as it was not possible to determine whether there was a reduction in recidivism or if the initiative was able to ensure rights.

No initiative was identified as having exclusively negative impacts, indicating that, overall, the evaluated initiatives contributed positively, albeit to varying degrees of intensity.

Below, the impacts of the initiatives are presented according to their purposes, highlighting the impact assessment, and detailing the objectives, strategies, and assumptions of each.

Detail of the Impacts

In this section, we will discuss the impacts of the initiatives, distinguishing them by focus and objectives. Of the six initiatives recognized for their positive impact, two are related to individual autonomy and social interaction, two to housing, one to productive inclusion, and one to health. It is worth noting that all initiatives with exclusively positive impacts are international, with no Brazilian initiatives falling into this category. Of these six, four assess the effects of the initiatives on recidivism, one on the guarantee of rights, and one addresses both aspects, being classified as mixed. It is important to emphasize that, while the expected effect in initiatives aimed at reducing recidivism is more specific and measurable, such as reentry into the prison system, the valuation of impact in initiatives focused on the guarantee of rights tends to be more subjective and difficult to quantify due to its broader and more comprehensive nature.

INDIVIDUAL AUTONOMY AND SOCIAL INTERACTION

Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme (United Kingdom)

Impact Assessment - Positive

- **Objective:** The **Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme** is a comprehensive reintegration service offered by the organization Pact, targeting women leaving prison. Funded by the City Bridge Trust, the Colyer-Fergusson Charitable Trust, and the London Housing Foundation, the program was launched in March 2021 and provides intensive, personalized support to women exiting four prisons located in Surrey and Kent.
- **Target Audience:** Formerly incarcerated and pre-release women.
- **Action Strategies:** The program operates in three key stages: pre-release, release day, and in the community. Each woman is supported by a reintegration officer who helps create a personal action plan. Pre-release interventions are conducted to prepare them for the challenges they will face after leaving prison. On release day, women are met by their reintegration officer, who assists them with housing acquisition, financial management, attendance at critical appointments, seeking employment or education, and strengthening family ties. They also receive an essentials package, access to welfare subsidies, online training, and ongoing support to facilitate their reintegration.
- **Assumption:** The Journeys 2 Freedom Programme aims to generate a positive impact on the lives of participating women by improving their living conditions and overall well-being. It also seeks to enhance collaboration among the services involved, including the justice, health, education, and social assistance sectors.
- **Evaluation Focus:** Rights assurance.
- **Impact of the Initiative:** The Journeys 2 Freedom Programme achieved positive results, with 95% of women in stable housing and 67% employed by the end of the support period. Additionally, in all cases involving legal issues, contact with children was successfully reestablished. Key factors contributing to this impact included the support provided by resettlement officers, who facilitated access to justice, health, and housing services, as well as the creation of individualized action plans. Emotional and practical support, interagency collaboration, and access to training opportunities also played a significant role in boosting the women's confidence and self-esteem, fostering their successful reintegration into society.

Community Mediation Maryland's Prisoner Reentry Program (United States)

Impact Assessment - Positive

- **Objective:** The **Community Mediation Maryland (CMM) Reentry Mediation Program** was designed to facilitate the transition of pre-release individuals by strengthening family ties and support networks. Implemented in the United States, the program is funded and managed by a civil society organization. Launched in 2008, it serves incarcerated individuals within 18 months of their release from penitentiary units in the state of Maryland and remains active today.

- **Target Audience:** Pre-release individuals and their families.

- **Action Strategies:** The program provides support to pre-release individuals and their families or people close to the beneficiaries by creating a space to discuss past experiences, foster mutual understanding, and jointly plan for reintegration into family and community structures before release.

- **Assumption:** Participation in the Community Mediation Maryland (CMM) Reentry Mediation program seeks to strengthen family bonds, contributing to the reduction of recidivism.

- **Evaluation Focus:** Recidivism.

- **Impact of the Initiative:** The evaluation conducted with formerly incarcerated individuals showed positive post-release impacts. Mediation reduced the likelihood of re-incarceration by 13%. For each additional mediation session, the probability of conviction decreased by 9%, while the probability of being sentenced to a period of incarceration of one day or more was reduced by 7%. Among recidivists monitored by the Department of Corrections, participants in mediation demonstrated a 12% lower risk of reoffending compared to non-participants. Additionally, the program reduced the likelihood of incarceration by 10%, with an additional 6% reduction per additional session. An increase in the time interval until re-incarceration was also observed, though this difference was not statistically significant.

Programa de Inclusão Social de Egressos do Sistema Prisional (Brazil)

Impact Assessment - Inconclusive

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- **Objective:** The **Programa de Inclusão Social de Egressos do Sistema Prisional** is a state initiative implemented in Minas Gerais, officially launched in 2006, with some earlier activities beginning in 2004. Its goal is to promote the social inclusion of individuals who have experienced incarceration through actions that restore citizenship and minimize the stigma and deprivation resulting from the prison experience, thereby reducing the likelihood of reoffending.

- **Target Audience:** Formerly incarcerated individuals and their families.

- **Action Strategies:** The program aims to ensure access to rights through psychosocial and legal assistance, complemented by referrals for professional training and integration into social support networks. These strategies seek to expand opportunities for formerly incarcerated individuals in the labor market, promoting their social reintegration.

- **Assumption:** Participation in the PrEsp program facilitates access to employment, professional training, and social rights, contributing to the reduction of recidivism.

- **Evaluation Focus:** Recidivism and rights assurance.

- **Impact of the Initiative:** In Belo Horizonte, where the program's implementation was analyzed, the prison reentry rate was 23%. However, no official data sources were presented for comparison. The absence of an experimental study with a control group prevented an evaluation of the program's impact on recidivism among non-participating formerly incarcerated individuals. The analysis found that young individuals and those with prior criminal records showed a higher likelihood of recidivism, highlighting the need for PrEsp to address specific issues related to youth and criminal trajectories. Additionally, the evaluation was unable to determine whether participants completed courses, enrolled in educational institutions, or accessed other key aspects necessary to infer the assurance of fundamental rights. The lack of a consolidated official database on recidivism and the absence of control groups also limited the comparative analysis with the presented recidivism rate. Therefore, the evaluation was classified as inconclusive.

HOUSING

Reentry Housing Pilot Program (United States)

Impact Assessment - Positive

- **Objective:** The **Reentry Housing Pilot Program** (RHPP) was a statewide program implemented in Washington, United States. Launched in 2007 and funded by the state, the program aimed to reduce criminal recidivism by providing up to 12 months of housing assistance to high-risk, high-need formerly incarcerated individuals without viable housing options. Assistance was conditional on participation in health treatments, job searching, and progress toward self-sufficiency. The program was discontinued due to funding cuts caused by the fiscal crisis stemming from the recession. No evaluation was conducted during its implementation, with the assessment being conducted only after the program was discontinued.

- **Target Audience:** High-risk, high-need formerly incarcerated individuals experiencing housing instability.

- **Action Strategies:** Provision of housing assistance conditional on participation in treatments, employment acquisition, and pursuit of self-sufficiency.

- **Assumption:** Access to improved housing conditions through the program reduces recidivism.

- **Evaluation Focus:** Recidivism.

- **Impact of the Initiative:** The results indicate that the RHPP program significantly reduced both new convictions and recidivism, although it had no substantial impact on the revocation of community supervision measures. Additionally, the analysis found that periods of homelessness significantly increase the risk of recidivism, whether through new convictions, revocations of community supervision, or readmissions to prison. Participants in the RHPP showed lower recidivism rates compared to the non-participant group: 21.6% of participants had new convictions (compared to 35.6% in the control group, with a statistically significant difference, $p = 0.002$), and 37% were readmitted to prison (compared to 56.3%, $p < 0.001$). However, the rate of revocation of community supervision measures was similar between groups (39.9% in the RHPP group versus 47.1% in the control group). Lastly, the program also reduced periods of homelessness: 18.3% of participants faced homelessness, compared to 26.3% in the control group ($p = 0.045$).

Vision Housing (United Kingdom)

Impact Assessment - Positive

- **Objective:** The **Vision Housing** program was established in January 2007 as a charitable organization and social enterprise based in London, currently operating under contracts with various public agencies. The program targets formerly incarcerated individuals and those serving or who have recently completed community sentences. Founded and largely operated by formerly incarcerated people, the program focuses on providing housing and support to individuals facing multiple issues, such as debt, substance abuse, domestic violence, gang involvement, and mental and physical health problems.
- **Target Audience:** Formerly incarcerated individuals and those serving or who have recently completed community sentences.
- **Action Strategies:** The initiative begins by providing housing, typically on the same day of release. Vision Housing maintains a broad network of landlords in London willing to accept formerly incarcerated individuals as tenants, ensuring direct and immediate payments to landlords. The program also conducts monthly property inspections.
- **Assumption:** Access to improved housing conditions through the program contributes to the reduction of recidivism.
- **Evaluation Focus:** Recidivism.
- **Impact of the Initiative:** The program demonstrated effectiveness in reducing recidivism among its participants. In an analysis of 400 participants evaluated over 12 months, the actual recidivism rate was 37.0%, compared to a forecasted rate of 40.7%, representing a statistically significant reduction of 9.1%. The program was particularly effective for women, individuals under 35 years old, high-risk offenders, and those referred by the Prison and Probation Service. In a two-year analysis of 271 participants, the actual recidivism rate was 49.0%, compared to a forecasted rate of 55.3%, resulting in a statistically significant reduction of 11.4%. These findings indicate that the program's positive impact is sustainable over time.

Returning Home - Ohio (United States)

Impact Assessment - Moderate

- **Objective:** The **Returning Home – Ohio** program is a state initiative implemented and funded by the Ohio Department of Rehabilitation and Correction (ODRC). Launched in 2006, the program aims to reduce criminal recidivism and housing instability by providing assisted housing to formerly incarcerated individuals from 13 state prisons in five cities across Ohio. The target audience includes individuals with mental and behavioral health conditions, as well as those with a history of housing instability or at imminent risk of homelessness. The program, which remains active, has housed over 100 individuals in the community over an approximate two-year period.

- **Target Audience:** Formerly incarcerated individuals with mental and behavioral health conditions, as well as those with a history of housing instability or at risk of homelessness.

- **Action Strategies:** The program provides assisted housing for individuals diagnosed with mental and behavioral health conditions, as well as those with a history of housing instability or at risk of homelessness upon release from 13 state prisons in five cities across Ohio.

- **Assumption:** Participation in the program, by providing access to improved housing conditions, contributes to reducing recidivism.

- **Evaluation Focus:** Recidivism.

- **Impact of the Initiative:** The program contributed to a 40% reduction in the likelihood of re-incarceration and a 61% reduction in the risk of imprisonment within one year. Additionally, program participation reduced arrests for minor offenses by 43%, although no significant impact was identified for arrests involving serious offenses. The program's success was attributed to the strong partnership between the ODRC and community providers, bolstered by continuous training. This strategic collaboration, described as pairing “the right people with the right providers,” was identified as a key factor in achieving positive outcomes. However, the program faced challenges in serving individuals with substance use or personality disorders, who are part of the program's priority audience. These groups showed less favorable outcomes, indicating that the program had no significant positive impact on this segment. While the program demonstrated promising results in reducing recidivism, difficulties in addressing the needs of populations with more complex disorders suggest a need for strategy adjustments to maximize its impact on these specific groups.

PRODUCTIVE INCLUSION

Skill Mill (United Kingdom and Estonia)

Impact Assessment - Positive

- **Objective:** The **Skill Mill** program was established in Newcastle, United Kingdom, and has expanded to other cities both in the UK and Estonia. Its primary goal is to help young offenders exiting the juvenile justice system desist from crime through productive inclusion. The initiative was developed in collaboration with public and private organizations, including the Environment Agency, Northumbrian Water Ltd., and Newcastle City Council. The program targets young individuals supervised by the Newcastle Youth Offending Team (YOT) who do not pose a high risk and have completed community service, requiring their voluntary participation.
- **Target Audience:** Young offenders aged 16 to 18.
- **Action Strategies:** The program provides opportunities for education and professional training in outdoor work, focusing on watercourse management and horticulture. Services include cleaning bodies of water, planting trees, gardening, waste removal, and implementing flood prevention measures.
- **Assumption:** Participation in the Skill Mill program and access to employment opportunities contribute to reducing recidivism.
- **Evaluation Focus:** Recidivism and rights assurance.
- **Impact of the Initiative:** The program demonstrated a significant reduction in recidivism among young offenders. On average, there were 1.12 fewer offenses per youth per quarter compared to the control group, with an additional reduction of 0.99 offenses per youth following the start of professional activities. Among participants who reoffended, the offenses committed were of less severity. The program's success is attributed to the combination of meaningful employment, competitive remuneration, civic engagement, and effective supervision. These elements provided mentorship, personal support, and a sense of community belonging. The model has been replicated in other cities across the United Kingdom and in Estonia, highlighting its potential as an effective tool to promote positive change and reduce youth criminality.

Ban the Box (United States)

Impact Assessment - Mixed

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- **Objective:** The **Ban the Box** (BTB) program is a U.S. government initiative aimed at expanding employment opportunities for individuals with criminal records, particularly formerly incarcerated individuals. It focuses specifically on Black men, who are disproportionately affected by their criminal records and exclusion from the labor market. Initially launched in the state of Hawaii in 1998, the program gained national prominence in 2003. Since then, it has been implemented in 35 states and over 150 municipalities, with funding from various levels of government (federal, state, and local). Its primary goal is to allow candidates to present their qualifications before being evaluated based on their criminal records, increasing employment opportunities and reducing racial disparities in the labor market.
- **Action Strategies:** The initiative proposes removing questions about criminal history from job application forms, postponing background checks to later stages in the selection process.
- **Target Audience:** Formerly incarcerated individuals..
- **Assumption:** The **Ban the Box** policy improves the inclusion of individuals with criminal records in the labor market.
- **Evaluation Focus:** Rights assurance.
- **Impact of the Initiative:** Research on the impact of BTB reveals mixed results, highlighting both benefits and unintended consequences. On one hand, the policy increased employment opportunities by up to 4% for residents of high-crime neighborhoods and raised public-sector employment probabilities for individuals with criminal records by 4 percentage points, representing an average 30% increase for this group, particularly in low-wage sectors. On the other hand, BTB intensified racial discrimination in the labor market. A 3.4% increase in discrimination was observed against Black candidates without criminal records, while the likelihood of Black candidates with criminal records being called for interviews rose by 6%. For White candidates without criminal records, the chances of being called increased by 5.3%. Additionally, BTB reduced employment probabilities by 3.4 percentage points for young Black men without college degrees and by 2.3 points for young Hispanic men without degrees, indicating that the policy may exacerbate discrimination against vulnerable groups. While BTB offers significant benefits for formerly incarcerated individuals and residents of high-crime areas, the data suggest it may also deepen racial inequalities, negatively affecting the employment prospects of certain demographic groups without criminal records.

HEALTH

Transitions Clinic Network (United States)

Impact Assessment - Positive

- **Objective:** The **Transitions Clinic Network** (TCN) is a national consortium of 45 primary care programs implemented in community health centers across 14 states in the United States. It was created to address the healthcare needs of individuals recently released from prison, particularly those with chronic health conditions or aged 50 and older. The program is funded through state Medicaid, which covers healthcare service costs but does not include expenses such as community health worker salaries or logistical needs.
- **Target Audience:** Formerly incarcerated individuals with chronic health conditions or aged 50 and older.
- **Action Strategies:** TCN offers enhanced primary care services to individuals with chronic health conditions or aged 50 and older. Participation is voluntary, and referrals come from prison systems, community service providers, or the individuals themselves.
- **Assumption:** Access to primary healthcare can reduce future contact with the criminal justice system among recently released individuals with chronic medical conditions.
- **Evaluation Focus:** Recidivism.
- **Impact of the Initiative:** The evaluation showed that the likelihood of recidivism, including arrests and new convictions, was similar between the treatment and control groups. However, participants in the Transitions Clinic Network had lower odds of returning to prison for violations of parole or supervised release (adjusted odds ratio (OR): 0.38; 95% CI: 0.16–0.93) compared to the control group. Additionally, among those who reoffended or returned to prison, the duration of incarceration was shorter (incidence rate ratio: 0.55; 95% CI: 0.35–0.84). These results indicate that the enhanced primary care offered by the program can reduce re-incarceration for violations of supervised release and decrease the length of time spent in custody.

Final Considerations

This study focused on identifying which strategies are effective for the social reintegration of formerly incarcerated individuals. To determine the nine initiatives with positive or mixed impacts, 128 publications on 83 initiatives were analyzed, highlighting that this area, in addition to being neglected in public policies – particularly in Brazil – lacks systematic evaluations to support and improve existing initiatives. Although some initiatives have demonstrated positive impacts and a higher volume of published evaluations, the majority are concentrated in foreign countries, suggesting that Brazilian policies still face significant limitations in terms of funding, implementation, and outcome evaluation.

The analysis underscores the need for continuous and rigorous evaluation of initiatives and policies targeting formerly incarcerated individuals. This process helps identify what works, for whom, and under what conditions, aiming to inspire the expansion of successful initiatives and break cycles of violence.

Incorporating an evaluative approach into initiatives and public policies not only provides input for continuous improvement but also ensures the production of reliable data. Particularly in the area of actions aimed at supporting individuals exiting the prison system – a historically neglected field – the consistent generation of knowledge about the implementation of initiatives is essential for understanding progress, fostering institutional learning, and improving decision-making processes.

The analysis of the initiatives revealed impacts in key areas of the post-release period, such as individual autonomy and social interaction, productive inclusion, health, and housing. Of the nine initiatives analyzed, five demonstrated positive impacts, standing out for achieving concrete results such as reducing recidivism and improving living conditions. Initiatives focused on individual autonomy and social interaction, such as **Community Mediation Maryland** and **Journeys 2 Freedom**, showed considerable progress in social reintegration, each adopting distinct approaches to support their target audiences.

Additionally, initiatives like **Skill Mill**, **Reentry Housing Pilot Program**, and **Vision Housing** illustrated the effectiveness of strategies centered on productive inclusion and housing assistance, with evidence of reduced recidivism and improvements in the socioeconomic conditions of formerly incarcerated individuals. Evaluations of these initiatives employed consistent methodologies, such as control groups and advanced statistical analyses, ensuring the reliability of the results and allowing inferences about the factors contributing to their success.

On the other hand, initiatives like **Returning Home – Ohio**, **Programa de Inclusão Social de Egressos do Sistema Prisional (PrEsp)**, and **Ban the Box** revealed mixed, moderate, or inconclusive impacts. This highlights the need for more precise approaches to achieve the intended objectives during their implementation, as well as broader evaluations to measure their outcomes. While no initiative was classified as having exclusively negative impacts, the analyses emphasized the importance of combining methodologies to capture the complexity of interventions, particularly in more challenging contexts.

Without consistent data, the ability to evaluate initiatives is limited, compromising both institutional learning and informed decision-making. Promoting a culture of monitoring and evaluation goes beyond short-term measurement – it involves building an evaluation system that ensures the quality, transparency, and effectiveness of public policies and social initiatives.

Although the implementation and evaluation of initiatives aimed at the social reintegration of formerly incarcerated individuals demonstrate the pressing need for investment in this area, the volume of allocated resources reflects a mismatch between the magnitude of the problem and the institutional responses offered. To make social reintegration effective, decision-makers must commit to this agenda by ensuring adequate resources for financing policies targeting this group.

Once resources are secured and prioritized, this publication sought to highlight the types of initiatives that should receive investment. However, it is evident that this area requires greater experimentation, accompanied by rigorous evaluations capable of measuring the real impacts of interventions and identifying what effectively contributes to the social reintegration of formerly incarcerated individuals.

Annexes

Annex I. Methodology

This section outlines the methodological procedures adopted for the development of this publication, including the following stages: analysis of publications on initiatives targeting formerly incarcerated individuals to identify evaluations, categorization of evaluative publications, data collection from these publications, and descriptive and diagnostic analysis of the results.

The database used for this publication is the same as that which supported the Guide for the Social Inclusion of Formerly Incarcerated Individuals,²⁵ published by the Igarapé Institute in 2024. Regarding the data sources of the analyzed publications, 128 publications were identified from 54 diverse sources, with a higher concentration in the following repositories and websites: National Council of Justice,²⁶ Medline,²⁷ Nacro,²⁸ Researchgate,²⁹ Capes Journals,³⁰ Criminal Justice Periodical Index³¹ and Global Center on Cooperative Security.³²

For this study, which focuses on evaluating the initiatives mentioned in the Guide, we initially analyzed 128 publications related to 83 initiatives. Data collection was conducted manually through an exhaustive search in national and international databases, using the following keywords:

Portuguese

Avaliação; Ressocialização; Socialização; Inclusão; Reinclusão; Reinserção; Inserção; Integração; Reintegração; Reabilitação; Medida; Projeto; Programa; Política; Oportunidade; Acesso; Serviço; Apoio; Assistência; Prisão; Cárcere; Presídio; Depois da prisão; Pós-prisão; Saída; Encarceramento; Sistema prisional; Sistema penitenciário; Penitenciária; Egressos; Encarcerado; Condenado; Ex-presidiários; Ex-presos; Trabalho; Emprego; Profissão; Renda; Educação; Estigma; Preconceito; Discriminação; Moradia; Alojamento; Habitação; Transporte; Mobilidade urbana; Saúde; Drogadição; Drogas; Dependentes químicos; Dependência; Legal; Jurídica; Social; Recidência; Prevenção; Direito; Público; Governo; Estadual; Municipal; Reentrada; Reencarceramento; Convívio (e suas variações no plural).

English

Assessment; Evaluation; Resocialization; Socialization; Inclusion; Reinclusion; Reinsertion; Insertion; Integration; Reintegration; Rehabilitation; Measure; Project; Program; Policy; Opportunity; Access; Service; Support; Assistance; Prison; After prison; Post-prison; Out of prison; Incarceration; Prison system; Penitentiary; Egress; Imprisoned; Condemned; Incarcerated; Formerly/ Previously incarcerated/convicted individuals/persons; Former inmates; Ex-convicts; Ex-prisoners; Work; Employment; Job; Income; Education; Stigma; Prejudice; Discrimination; Housing; Transportation; Urban mobility; Health; Drug addiction; Drugs; Chemical dependents; Dependency; Legal; Social; Recidivism; Prevention; Right; Public; Government; State; Municipal; Reentry; Reincarceration; Conviviality (and their plural variations).

Source: Prepared by the Igarapé Institute based on proprietary data.

The data processing for this database was structured by separating evaluated initiatives from those without evaluation. To identify publications that included evaluations of initiatives targeting formerly incarcerated individuals, the following characteristics were considered: description of evaluation criteria, description of the methodology used, and presentation of results and conclusions based on evidence.

After this initial selection, the focus shifted to identifying, within the set of publications with evaluations, those that met the analysis criteria established for this study:

- Timeframe: From 2013 to 2023.
- Access: Open and free of charge.
- Content: Discussion on the effects, either impact and/or process, of the implementation of the initiative, excluding publications limited to theoretical debates.

This process resulted in 32 publications (evaluative publication sample) that met the established criteria. These 32 publications filtered according to methodological criteria correspond to evaluations of 21 initiatives.

For data collection, a structured form was developed to gather information available in the evaluative publications of initiatives targeting formerly incarcerated individuals. This form included questions about the description of the publication, the evaluated initiative, the application of the evaluation, the methodology used, and the results obtained.

Based on 32 evaluative publications on 21 national and international initiatives, we conducted a detailed analysis of those presenting impact evaluations (17 in total), including one that simultaneously addressed both impact and process. From these 17, 13 publications related to nine initiatives were selected for meeting the established methodological robustness criteria, considering metrics, techniques, sample selection, and intervention period.

METHODOLOGICAL FUNNEL

1. PUBLICATION IDENTIFICATIONS

128 publications on 83 initiatives

total publications found on initiatives analyzed in the Guide for the Social Inclusion of Formerly Incarcerated Individuals.

2. EVALUATION IDENTIFICATION AND METHODOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION

32 evaluative publications on 21 initiatives

sample

3. APPLICATION OF EVALUATION FOCUS AND ROBUSTNESS CRITERIA

13 evaluative publications on 9 initiatives

subsample

4. IMPACT ANALYSIS OF INITIATIVES

9 initiatives were analyzed, of which:

- **6** showed a positive impact
- **1** a moderate impact
- **1** a mixed impact
- **1** an inconclusive impact

Annex II. General Framework of the 21 initiatives with Evaluations

Country of Implementation	Initiative	Purpose	Implemented by	Funded by
Brazil	Casa das Juventudes (Projeto Proteção de Jovens em Território Vulnerável – Protejo)	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Casa de Acolhida – Centro Social Nossa Senhora Aparecida	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Civil society organization	Public Sector
	Escritório Social ³³	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Projeto Alvorada	Productive Inclusion	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Programa de Atenção ao Egresso e Família	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Projeto Começar de Novo ³⁴	Productive Inclusion	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Programa de Inclusão Social de Egressos do Sistema Prisional (PrEsp)	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Projeto Regresso ³⁵	Productive Inclusion	Civil society organization	Public Sector
	Projeto Migrantes Egressas (PME)	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Public Sector and Civil society organization	Public and Private Sector, and Civil society organization

Country of Implementation	Initiative	Purpose	Implemented by	Funded by
United States	Ban the Box	Productive Inclusion	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Community Mediation Maryland (CMM) Reentry Mediation	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Civil society organization	Civil society organization
	Health Homes	Health	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Medicaid	Health	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Reentry Housing Pilot Program (RHPP)	Housing	Public Sector	Public Sector
	Returning Home - Ohio	Housing	Public Sector and Civil society organization	Public Sector
	Transitions Clinic Network (TCN)	Health	Public Sector	Public Sector
New Zealand	Tiaki Tangata - Project Kete	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Sector público y privado	Sector público
	Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme	Individual Autonomy and Social Interaction	Civil society organization	Public and Private Sector, and Civil society organization
United Kingdom	Skill Mill	Productive Inclusion	Civil society organization	Public and Private Sector, and Civil society organization
	Vision Housing	Housing	Civil society organization	Civil society organization
	Working Chance	Productive Inclusion	Civil society organization	Public and Private Sector, and Civil society organization

Annex III. General Framework of the 32 Evaluative Publications

Initiative	Type of Evaluation Publication	Name of the Evaluation Publication	Who Evaluated the Initiative?	Who funded the Initiative?	Evaluation Focus	Methodological Approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Casa das Juventudes (Projeto Proteção de Jovens em Território Vulnerável – Protejo) 	Scientific article	Ampliação do campo de possibilidade de jovens em vulnerabilidade social: a experiência da Casa das Juventudes	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Qualitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Casa de Acolhida – Centro Social Nossa Senhora Aparecida 	Scientific article	Casa das mulheres: refugiadas, estrangeiras egressas do sistema penitenciário e políticas de acolhida em São Paulo, Brasil	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Qualitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Escritório Social 	Scientific article	Superando o estigma da prisão e efetivação de direitos e cidadania: contribuições da psicologia na promoção de trabalho aos Egressos do sistema de justiça	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Mixed

Initiative	Type of Evaluation Publication	Name of the Evaluation Publication	Who Evaluated the Initiative?	Who funded the Initiative?	Evaluation Focus	Methodological Approach
• Projeto Alvorada ³⁶	Academic work	Egressos do sistema prisional: Há possibilidade de reinserção no convívio social pela educação profissional?	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Qualitative
	Scientific article	O Projeto Alvorada, do Instituto Federal de Goiás: ressocialização de egressos do sistema prisional	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Qualitative
	Scientific article	Projeto Alvorada: Inclusão produtiva de pessoas egressas do sistema prisional	Academia	Not mentioned	Both: Recidivism and Rights Assurance	Qualitative
• Programa de Atenção ao Egresso e Família	Academic work	A reinserção social na perspectiva de egressos de penitenciárias e profissionais das Centrais de Atenção ao Egresso e à Família	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Qualitative
• Projeto Começar de Novo	Final and internal report	Começar de Novo e Escritório Social: Estratégia de Convergência	State and international organization	Estado y organización internacional	Rights Assurance	Mixed

Initiative	Type of Evaluation Publication	Name of the Evaluation Publication	Who Evaluated the Initiative?	Who funded the Initiative?	Evaluation Focus	Methodological Approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programa de Inclusão Social de Egressos do Sistema Prisional (PrEsp) 	Scientific article	A influência de programas de apoio a egressos do sistema prisional na redução da reentrada prisional	Academia	Not mentioned	Both: Recidivism and Rights Assurance	Qualitative
	Scientific article	Entre a cruz e a espada: a reintegração de egressos do sistema prisional a partir da política pública do governo de Minas Gerais	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Qualitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projeto Regresso 	Scientific article	Egressos do sistema prisional no mercado formal de trabalho: Oportunidade real de inclusão social?	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Mixed
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projeto Migrantes Egressas (PME) 	Scientific article	Projeto migrantes egressas: uma experiência de trabalho de organização da sociedade civil com mulheres migrantes em conflito com a lei na cidade de São Paulo	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Qualitative

Initiative	Type of Evaluation Publication	Name of the Evaluation Publication	Who Evaluated the Initiative?	Who funded the Initiative?	Evaluation Focus	Methodological Approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ban the Box 	Research report	Ban the Box, Convictions, and Public Employment	Academia	Academia	Rights Assurance	Quantitative
	Scientific article	Ban the Box, Criminal Records, And Statistical Discrimination: A Field Experiment	Academia	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Quantitative
	Scientific article	Ban the Box' Measures Help High-crime Neighborhoods	Civil society organization	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Quantitative
	Scientific article	The unintended consequences of "ban the box": Statistical discrimination and employment outcomes when criminal histories are hidden	Academia	Academia	Rights Assurance	Quantitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community Mediation Maryland (CMM) Reentry Mediation 	Research report	Community Mediation Maryland Reentry Mediation In-Depth Recidivism Analysis	Business consultancy	Civil society organization	Recidivism	Quantitative
	Research report	Community Mediation Maryland Reentry Mediation Recidivism Analysis	Business consultancy	Civil society organization	Recidivism	Quantitative

Initiative	Type of Evaluation Publication	Name of the Evaluation Publication	Who Evaluated the Initiative?	Who funded the Initiative?	Evaluation Focus	Methodological Approach
• Health Homes	Scientific article	Connecting Justice-Involved Individuals with Health Homes at Reentry: New York and Rhode Island	Civil society organization	State	Rights Assurance	Quantitative
• Medicaid	Informative document	Connecting the Justice-Involved Population to Medicaid Coverage and Care: Findings from Three States	Civil society organization	Civil society organization	Rights Assurance	Qualitative
• Reentry Housing Pilot Program (RHPP)	Scientific article	Homelessness and reentry: A Multisite Outcome Evaluation of Washington State’s Reentry Housing Program for High Risk Offenders	Academia	State	Recidivism	Quantitative
• Returning Home - Ohio	Scientific article	The Role of Supportive Housing in Successful Reentry Outcomes for Disabled Prisoners	Civil society organization	Not mentioned	Recidivism	Mixed

Initiative	Type of Evaluation Publication	Name of the Evaluation Publication	Who Evaluated the Initiative?	Who funded the Initiative?	Evaluation Focus	Methodological Approach
• Transitions Clinic Network (TCN)	Scientific article	Cost savings of a primary care program for individuals recently released from prison: a propensity-matched study	Academia	State	Rights Assurance	Quantitative
	Scientific article	Propensity-matched study of enhanced primary care on contact with the criminal justice system among individuals recently released from prison to New Haven	Academia	State	Recidivism	Quantitative
• Tiaki Tangata - Project Kete	Final and internal report	Offender Case Management: Tiaki Tangata-Project Kete	Civil society organization	Not mentioned	Both: Recidivism and Rights Assurance	Mixed
• Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme	Final and internal report	Journeys to Freedom. A report examining the need for and impact of Pact's holistic resettlement programme for women leaving prison	Civil society organization	Not mentioned	Rights Assurance	Mixed
• Skill Mill	Final and internal report	Interim Evaluation of the Skill Mill SIB	Academia	No menciona	Both: Recidivism and Rights Assurance	Mixed

Initiative	Type of Evaluation Publication	Name of the Evaluation Publication	Who Evaluated the Initiative?	Who funded the Initiative?	Evaluation Focus	Methodological Approach
• Skill Mill ³⁷	Scientific article	Do Flood Mitigation and Natural Habitat Protection Employment Reduce Youth Offending?	Academia	Not mentioned	Recidivism	Mixed
• Vision Housing	Research report	An evaluation of the effect of housing provision on re-offending	Academia	Not mentioned	Recidivism	Quantitative
• Working Chance	Final and internal report	Working Chance 2020/21 Report and financial statements for the year ended 31 August 2021	Civil society organization	Not mentioned	Both: Recidivism and Rights Assurance	Mixed
	Final and internal report	Working Chance 2021/22 Report and financial statements for the year ended 31 August 2022	Civil society organization	Not mentioned	Both: Recidivism and Rights Assurance	Mixed
	Final and internal report	Working Chance 2022/23 Report and financial statements for the year ended 31 August 2023	Civil society organization	Not mentioned	Both: Recidivism and Rights Assurance	Mixed

Source: Prepared by the Igarapé Institute based on proprietary data.

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Endnotes

1. Igarapé Institute (2024). [Guide for the Social Inclusion of Formerly Incarcerated Individuals](#)
2. Technical violations refer to non-compliance with conditions imposed on a person under probation, house arrest, parole, or other non-custodial sentencing regimes, without the commission of a new crime, such as failing to attend meetings with a probation officer or not fulfilling stipulated obligations.
3. European Court of Human Rights (2002). [Case of Mastromatteo v. Italy](#)
4. This study adopts the perspective of Alvino Augusto de Sá (2001), who argues that social reintegration should not be defined by the crime committed or the sentence imposed, but rather by the relationship between the incarcerated individual and their social context. For a more detailed analysis of the topic, the article *The Concept of Crime as an Expression of a History of Conflicts: Implications for the Social Reintegration of Those Sentenced to Incarceration*, published in the journal of the Higher School of the Judiciary of Santa Catarina (Esmesc), v. 7, n. 11, pp 169-178, 2001.
5. We understand that the concept of social (re)integration and its related terms are subjects of debate, as individuals targeted by the criminal justice system have historically faced inequalities and social exclusion.
6. Igarapé Institute (2022). [Recidivism and Re-entry Into Prison in Brazil: What Studies Say About the Factors That Contribute to This Trajectory](#)
7. Infopen (2024). [Levantamento Nacional de Informações Penitenciárias](#)
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9. O Justa (2024). [O funil de investimento da segurança pública e prisional no Brasil em 2022](#)
10. Some initiatives are mentioned in more than one evaluation document, as detailed in Table 4.
11. Support for pre-release individuals is characterized by transitional initiatives aimed at preparing those nearing release from the prison system for their transition to freedom or semi-liberty. These actions accompany individuals during the process of moving from incarceration to the status of former inmates. Notable initiatives in this context include: Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme, in the United Kingdom; Community Mediation Maryland (CMM) Reentry Mediation, in the U.S.; Returning Home - Ohio, in the U.S.; Transitions Clinic Network (TCN), in the U.S.; Vision Housing, in the United Kingdom; Working Chance, in the United Kingdom; Tiaki Tangata – Project Kete (Caring for People - Maori Support Project), in New Zealand; and the Projeto Migrantes Egressas (Formerly Incarcerated Migrant Reintegration Project), in Brazil.
12. Programa de Atenção ao Egresso e Família (Program for Assistance to Formerly Incarcerated Individuals and their Families), in Brazil, and Community Mediation Maryland (CMM) Reentry Mediation, in the United States.
13. Casa de Acolhida – Centro Social Nossa Senhora Aparecida (Shelter Home: Nossa Senhora Aparecida Social Center) and Projeto Migrantes Egressas (Formerly Incarcerated Migrant Women Reintegration Project), in Brazil; Journeys 2 Freedom: Women's Resettlement Programme e Working Chance, both in the United Kingdom.
14. Tiaki Tangata - Project Kete, in New Zealand.
15. Skill Mill and Casa das Juventudes – Projeto Proteção de Jovens em Território Vulnerável (Youth House - Project for Protection of Youth In Vulnerable Territories – Protejo), in Brazil.
16. Health Homes, in the United States.
17. Reentry Housing Pilot Program (RHPP), in the United States.
18. Fair, W. (2021). It is important to highlight that the methodological choice to analyze publications exclusively in Portuguese and English impacts the geographical distribution of the identified initiatives. This approach reflects the greater ease of finding discussions about initiatives in countries where these languages are predominant. Furthermore, this concentration is influenced by the fact that the United States has the largest prison population in the world and Brazil the third largest.
19. The classification of the purpose of the initiatives follows the framework established by the [Guide for the Social Inclusion of Formerly Incarcerated Individuals](#), mentioned earlier.
20. Trevisan y Van Bellen (2008). An impact evaluation is understood as one that measures the effects of an initiative, determining the changes directly attributable to the actions implemented. This type of evaluation analyzes the effects and impacts generated in society, establishing a clear cause-and-effect relationship between the program's interventions and the final outcomes achieved.
21. Trevisan y Van Bellen (2008). A process evaluation examines the implementation and operationalization of an initiative, analyzing how activities were carried out, adherence to the action plan, and the factors influencing its execution. It focuses on the internal mechanisms of the initiative, the barriers and obstacles identified for its reformulation, and the interactions between the initiative's components and its participants.
22. The evaluation encompassing both process and impact pertains to the initiative Casa das Juventudes. This classification is justified by the fact that the analysis goes beyond the outcomes achieved (impact), such as expanded opportunities within the life trajectories of participating adolescents and young adults. It also includes an assessment of the program's execution and implementation, evaluating how activities were carried out to achieve the proposed objectives (process).

23. One example is the evaluation “The Role of Supportive Housing in Successful Reentry Outcomes for Disabled Prisoners”, conducted by a think tank in the United States, which analyzed the Returning Home – Ohio program. The evaluation utilized data from the Ohio Department of Rehabilitation and Correction (ODRC), including demographic characteristics, incarceration history, and supervision status, employing a quasi-experimental design with propensity score weighting to investigate the program’s effectiveness in reducing recidivism. Another relevant case is the evaluation Community Mediation Maryland Reentry Mediation Recidivism, conducted by a business consultancy on the initiative Community Mediation Maryland (CMM). This analysis used data from the Department of Public Safety and Correctional Services (DPSCS), applying logistic regression to analyze recidivism and Cox regression to examine the time to reoffending. The models accounted for factors such as the duration of criminal careers and time since release, aiming to understand the impact of mediation on reducing recidivism.
24. Programa de Inclusão Social de Egressos do Sistema Prisional (PrEsp), in freely translation, means Social Inclusion Program for Formerly Incarcerated People (PrEsp).
25. The [Guide for the Social Inclusion of Formerly Incarcerated Individuals](#) selected 123 programs aimed at supporting individuals exiting the prison system from a database of 511 documents.
26. [National Council of Justice](#)
27. [Medline](#)
28. [Nacro](#)
29. [Researchgate](#)
30. [Capes Journals](#)
31. [Criminal Justice Periodical Index](#)
32. [Global Center on Cooperative Security](#)
33. Escritório Social, freely translated into English, means Social Office.
34. Projeto Começar de Novo, freely translated into English, means Fresh Start Program.
35. Projeto Regresso, freely translated into English, means return Project.
36. Projeto Alvorada, freely translated into English, means Alvorada Project.
37. As mentioned earlier, this evaluation was conducted in Estonia. However, since the initiative was implemented in both countries, it was counted among the evaluations from the United Kingdom.

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